

Unveiling the mass assembly history of the Milky Way via its stellar halo

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Stellar haloes are important galactic components that retain vital clues towards deciphering how galaxies assemble their mass and evolve over time. It is in these regions where the debris from disrupted satellite galaxies resulting from the hierarchical formation of galaxies – a fundamental prediction of Lambda Cold Dark Matter – are found, as well as the debris from dissolved/evaporated globular clusters (GC). Therefore, albeit it only amounting to $\sim 1\%$ of the total stellar mass in the Milky Way, the Galactic stellar halo is a pivotal region to study encoding many clues about our Galaxy formed and evolved.

The advent of large-scale stellar surveys, and specifically the *Gaia* mission, has revolutionised how we study the Galaxy. The ability to chemo-dynamically mark millions of stars in the Milky Way has enabled the characterisation of stellar populations in every region of the Galaxy. Of particular importance has been the discovery of phase space substructure in the Galactic stellar halo [1, 2, 3, 4], conjectured to be the remnants of past encounters between cannibalised satellite galaxies and/or disrupted GCs with the Milky Way. While such discoveries have helped tremendously in the efforts to disentangling how the Milky Way formed and evolved, there still remains a debate of how many past accretions the Galaxy encountered, and how much mass is comprised from accreted galaxies and/or disrupted GCs.

Accretion history of the Milky Way: Heracles

The central few kpc of the Galactic halo are obviously extremely important when it comes to retelling the early accretion history of the Milky Way and discerning the contribution of in situ formation to the stellar halo mass. This is because: *i*) it is within the central $\sim 3\text{-}4\text{ kpc}$ that approximately 50% of the mass of the stellar halo is contained; *ii*) it is the region one would expect to find the debris from massive and/or early accreted systems; *iii*) it is also the region one would expect to host most of the early in situ halo star formation, including the oldest stars in the Galaxy. However, observational access to inner halo populations is quite difficult due to dust extinction and overcrowding.

Here, we use the combination of APOGEE spectroscopy and *Gaia* astrometry to chemo-dynamically characterise stellar halo populations in the innermost regions of the Galaxy. Utilising a chemical dissection in the $[\text{Mg}/\text{Mn}]\text{-}[\text{Al}/\text{Fe}]$ plane, we split stellar populations likely formed in/ex-situ and then study their integrals of motion (IoM). Upon identifying a new overdensity in the "accreted" group, we set out to analyse its chemo-dynamical properties by comparing the chemical compositions and IoM with its co-spatial in-situ counterpart populations. We find that this new substructure (dubbed Heracles) presents chemo-dynamical properties that are consistent

with an accretion origin. Additionally, we perform several tests to assess the reality of Heracles, such as examining if it statistically can be modelled and as independent component in multiple 2D chemical planes, and contrasting its properties to expectations from the EAGLE cosmological simulations; we find that Heracles survives these tests, reinforcing our initial accreted scenario hypothesis. In summary, the properties of Heracles suggest it is the remnant of an early accreted and massive disrupted satellite galaxy [5].

Figure 1: An artist's impression of what the Milky Way might look like seen from above. The red rings show the rough extent of the fossil galaxy known as Heracles. The yellow dot shows the position of the Sun.

Revealing the reality and nature of halo substructures

In the past few years, several distinct satellite accretions have been suggested by various groups [1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8]. While the identification of these substructures is helping constrain our understanding of the mass assembly history of the Milky Way, their association with any particular accretion event still needs to be clarified. Along those lines, predictions from numerical simulations suggest that a single accretion event can lead to multiple substructures in phase space [9, 10]. Therefore, in order to ascertain the reality and/or distinction of these accretion events, one must resort to additional chemical composition information for large samples.

Here, we perform a detailed chemical composition comparison of halo substructure in the Milky Way (identified using selection techniques from previous work) using a homogeneous catalogue obtained by cross-matching the latest APOGEE and *Gaia* data [11]. By performing first a qualitative, and then second a quantitative comparison, we further disentangle the reality and nature of the following halo substructures: *Gaia*-

Enceladus/Sausage (GES), Heracles, Sagittarius dSph, Sequoia, Helmi stream, Thamnos, Aleph, LMS-1, Arjuna, l'itoi, Nyx, Icarus, and Pontus. A summary of our findings is shown in 2. In short, our results show that many halo substructures conjectured to be debris from individual accretions likely belong to either the omnipresent GES or to in situ populations, and that the Milky Way likely underwent three major mergers so far: Heracles, GES, Sagittarius dSph.

Figure 2: Confusion matrix of the χ^2 probability values obtained when comparing the chemical compositions of all the halo substructures with each other and with a high-/low- α discs. Here, each substructure is compared with its counterpart using a $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ value that is well covered by the data, where red(blue) signifies a high(low) probability of two systems being statistically equal given their chemical compositions. Comparisons with blank values are due to the two substructures being compared not having any overlap in $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$.

The mass contribution from globular clusters to the Galaxy

The contribution of dissolved and/or evaporated globular clusters (GC) to the stellar content of the Galaxy is a key constraint on models of GC formation and the mass assembly history of the Milky Way. Earlier results from APOGEE pointed to a large contribution of destroyed GCs to the stellar content of the inner halo [4], by as much as 25 per cent per cent, which is an order of magnitude larger than previous estimates for more distant regions [12]. We set out to measure the ratio between nitrogen-rich (N-rich, namely second population GC stars

now in the halo field) and normal halo field stars, as a function of distance, by performing density modelling of halo field populations in APOGEE DR16, accounting for the survey selection function effects. Our results show that at 1.5 kpc from the Galactic Centre, N-rich stars contribute a much higher $16.8^{+10}_{-7}\%$ fraction to the total stellar halo mass budget than the $2.7^{+1}_{-0.8}\%$ ratio contributed at 10 kpc [13]. Under the assumption that N-rich stars are former GC members that now reside in the stellar halo field, and assuming the ratio between first and second population GC stars being 1:2, we estimate a total contribution from disrupted GC stars of the order of $27.5^{+15.4}_{-11.5}\%$ at $r = 1.5$ kpc and $4.2^{+1.5}_{-1.3}\%$ at $r = 10$ kpc. Furthermore, we integrate such density within a spherical shell from 1.5 to 15 kpc in radius, and find a total stellar mass arising from dissolved and/or evaporated GCs of $M_{\text{GC, total}} = 9.6^{+4.0}_{-2.6} \times 10^7 M_{\odot}$.

Figure 3: Mass density percentage ratio of N-rich stars and halo field stars as a function of spherical radius, where black(grey) are the median($1-\sigma$) values; the dashed line indicates the Galactocentric distance range where the density is not well constrained due to low numbers of N-rich stars. See text for details.

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